

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers,

It gives me a great pleasure to announce the third regular issue of 2020. I want to thank all authors for contributing their sound research and the editorial board for the highly valuable review effort and comments for improvements. These contributions together with the generous support of the consortium members sustain the quality of our journal. In this regular issue, I am very pleased to introduce 9 accepted papers which have passed a rigorous peer-review process.

Alexsandro Oliveira Alexandrino, Andre Rodrigues Oliveira, Ulisses Dias, and Zanoni Dias from Brazil report in their article on their approach to finding a minimum cost sequence of rearrangements needed to transform one genome into another.

Daniel de Souza Baulé, Christiane Gresse von Wangenheim, Aldo von Wangenheim, and Jean C. R. Hauck from Brazil analyze and discuss in their contribution recent progress in automated code generation from GUI images by means of machine learning techniques.

In a collaborative research between India, Turkey and Lithuania, Ranjan Kumar Behera, Sushree Das, Santanu Kumar Rath, Sanjay Misra, and Robertas Damasevicius propose and discuss various machine learning models which predict the stock price from the real-time streaming data.

Tony Clark from the UK and Jens Gulden from The Netherlands review the current state of the art for modelling tools and propose a set of reflective meta-modelling tool requirements for designing and generating software.

Augusto C. de Castro Barbosa, Carlos A. de Moura, Jhoab P. de Negreiros, and J. Mesquita de Souza Aguiar from Brazil deal with the numerical treatment of a data completion problem in heat conduction modelling.

In a collaborative research between Austria and Eastland, Angela Fessler, Viktoria Pammer-Schindler, Kai Pata, Sandra Feyertag, Mati Mottus, Jörgen Janus, and Tobias Ley present cooperative design as method to address the needs of SMEs to gain sufficient knowledge about new technologies to decide about their adoption for knowledge management.

José L. Martín, Susana Sastre, José M. Peiró, and José Ramón Hilera from Spain discuss the effects of using a fully integrated mobile application to access learning management systems in higher education.

Emilio Rodríguez-Priego, Francisco J. García-Izquierdo and Ángel Luis Rubio from Spain present their proposal for an improved model for modeling, named Scientific Method approach to Modeling (SMM).

And last but not least, Shuangbu Wang, Yu Xia, Lihua You, and Jianjun Zhang from the United Kingdom propose an automatic method to extract curve segments and reconstruct curve networks from unorganized spatial points.

Enjoy Reading!

Cordially,

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Christian Gütl', with a stylized flourish at the end.

Christian Gütl, Managing Editor
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